

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER TECHNOLOGIES FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLE CHARGING

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Abstract

This Paper covers the design and construction of an Electric Vehicle system design, a two-wheeled electric vehicle. It works on the principle of conservation of angular momentum. The control signal was produced and sent to the motor controller. The motor controller drives the motor at the specified speed, torque, and direction. This paper also explains the working as well as component selection for various electronic components such as the Motor, Gate box driven, the principle of self-balancing and the controller can be used to achieve the same.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle, PID Controller, Embedded system design, Motor control.

1. INTRODUCTION

Humanity is depleting its fossil fuel reserves, so when they are exhausted, a transition to green alternatives like electric vehicles, which produce no CO₂ emissions, will be essential. Among various charging technologies, WPT has been one of the ideal solutions in eradicating traditional plug-in EV power systems due to inherent limitations such as time consumption for a full charge and infrastructure inadequacy. Remove any physical connections, increase comfort and safety and reduce wear on components with WPT.

Wireless Power Transfer systems originally demonstrated by Nikola Tesla in 1891 are categorized into short-air-gap and long air gap system. Lower frequencies, higher magnetic coupling and shorter air gaps make short-air-gap systems the winning solution for inductive charging of EVs at distances of 10–40cm between transmitter and receiver. There are also multiple charging methods for EVs, from slow home chargers through to fast public station charge points.

Wireless power transfer systems for EVs can both be static (charging while parked) and dynamic (powering the vehicle on-the-go). Dynamic charging is high-speeds vehicle friendly and because it reduces battery size too, leading to higher range in electric cars. But expensive as a technology compared against wireless static charging option. Coil misalignment and varying distances that reduce efficiency are two obstacles, though new coil designs (for coils), magnetic resonance coupling techniques address these problems. Research in high-frequency WPT systems has been conducted with the objectives of improving efficiency, reducing complexity of the system, and increasing reliability. Such a novel

approach involves the application of multi-layer, non-uniform self-resonant coils that would strengthen magnetic coupling while keeping PTE at a high level. Thus, this will make EV charging more efficient and scalable to support the broader adoption of wireless charging. While there are several short-range applications of wireless power transfer for EVs, CPT has been limited in its effectiveness due to misalignment and efficiency loss at larger distances. However, recent advancements in magnetic resonance coupling, impedance matching, and surface routing show great potential. Capacitive Power Transfer provides another option with safety and cost advantages; however, it is limited to shorter distances. The static as well as dynamic WPT technologies for EVs are among the major milestones toward sustainable transportation that reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and clear the path toward a cleaner future.

Figure 1 Basic Structure of WPT System

2. KEY CONTRIBUTIONS OF THIS RESEARCH INCLUDE

A new high-quality self-resonant coil design for high-frequency applications and modeling and optimization methods for coil geometry. It has been done using a 6.6

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kW system in the MHz region to prove this aspect for EV charging with high frequency, high power WPT system. A viable shielding solution for the self-resonant coil was developed, representing the first instance of utilizing a well-shielded small coil in a 6.6 kW WPT system.

Detailed analysis and selection criteria for the optimum multi-layer coil configurations for WPT applications. To summarize, these papers collectively enhance the knowledge and WPT technology development mainly concerning efficiency improvement, safety enhancement, and more practical application in the charging processes of electric vehicles and other electronic gadgets. Fig.2. shows the block diagram of the WPT system.

Figure 2 Block Diagram of WPT System

3. METHODOLOGIES

There are various methods for WPT, which depend on the technology being used and the frequency of transmission. These two have been categorized into 1) Near-field coupling, and 2) Radiative far field. The coupling type near-field is further classified into two types; magnetic field and electric field, while the radiative type is classified into microwave and laser types as shown in the figure.

Figure.3. shows the WPT techniques and their operational range concerning the air gap and frequency. With an increase in frequency, the dimensions of both transmitter and receiver increase

Figure 3 Classification of WPT Methods

Inductive WPT

An Inductive Wireless Power Transfer (IWPT) system uses electromagnetic waves for operation. The working principle is similar to that of a conventional transformer. On the primary side, Ampere's law dictates that AC creates a magnetic field around the wire (primary side coupler). This changing magnetic field is then passed on to the magnetic coupler on the secondary side. According to Faraday's law, this magnetic field induces a voltage in the secondary coil. Figure.4. shows IWPT system block diagram. The induced voltage is then converted to DC power by the rectifier which can be used for charging

batteries. System efficiency improves by tuning secondary coil frequency to match operating frequency. For radio frequencies, air gap between coils can be increased up to 200 mm, but then efficiency decreases

Figure 4 Generic diagram of IWPT

Conductive WPT

Capacitive Wireless Power Transfer (CWPT) is a subtype of wireless power transfer that transmits energy via an electric field or electrostatic field. In CWPT, the power transmission occurs through an electric field established between two opposed metal plates. For the purpose of this study, sending and receiving plates have different sets. When subjected to voltage, the sending plates generate an electric field that the receiving plates utilize to produce current. Thus, very high yet low current applications are most suited for CWPT. Here, extra inductors are added with the plates as well - thus cutting down electrical resistance and enhancing effectiveness simultaneously. Figure.5. shows CWPT system block diagram. This also smooths out the switching process and hence boosts power transfer efficiency. The converted rectified received power charges batteries after being transformed into direct current (DC) by a rectifier. Moreover, CWPT systems are lighter in weight and more economical than IWPT systems

Figure 5 Generic diagram of CWPT

Resonant Inductive WPT

Resonant Inductive Wireless Power Transfer (RI-WPT) is a system that has been designed to allow the transfer of energy wirelessly between two coils separated at a short distance through the mechanism of resonant inductive coupling. In the case of EVs, the RI-WPT system establishes electromagnetic resonance between two coils, transmitter coil located at the charging station and receiver coil mounted on the electric vehicle. Transmitter Coil This coil connects to the power supply and creates a magnetic field whenever AC power flows through it. Receiver Coil this is placed on the underside of the electric vehicle; it captures energy from the magnetic field and converts it into electrical power to charge the battery. The efficiency in transferring energy hence will be very high since they have tuned both coils to operate at a similar frequency. To further enhance efficiency and reduce losses during transmission, general components such as compensation networks comprising capacitors or inductors have been added to both sides. Therefore, this technology can be easily implemented in parking spots, roads, or garages for

convenient and cable-free charging of EVs. Figure.6. shows RIWPT system block diagram

Figure 6 Generic diagram of RIWPT

4. MICRO WAVE / RADIO FREQUENCY

Among the various wireless power transfer techniques used for electric vehicles microwave and radio frequency (RF) are prominent. A transmitter transforms electrical energy to microwave or RF signals which are wirelessly sent to an EV having a receiving unit that transforms these signals again into electrical energy for charging it battery. A transmitter converts electrical energy into microwave or RF signals, which are sent wirelessly to an EV equipped with a receiving unit that converts these signals back into electrical energy to charge its battery. This technology makes use of wireless transmission of power and as such does away with the need of any physical charging connection; thus, simplifying the charging process and reducing wear on ports. Figure.7. shows Micro Wave WPT system block diagram.

There is potential for on-the-go charging, where vehicles can charge while driving on roads equipped with transmitter infrastructure. Current systems face efficiency losses during transmission, and high-power emissions need to be carefully regulated to avoid risks to humans and electronics. Additionally, developing the necessary infrastructure can be costly and may involve regulatory hurdles. Static Charging Stations: Traditional charging stations that operate without cables

Figure 7 Generic diagram of Micro Wave WPT

Dynamic Charging Systems: Embedded in roadways for charging while driving.

Public Infrastructure: It can be integrated into parking facilities or transit hubs to make it accessible with easy access to charging. In general, the WPT for EVs has a tremendous potential to improve charging comfort and effectiveness, although it needs to tackle a variety of technical as well as regulatory challenges

Light Wave

WPT for EVs using light waves emits LEDs or laser diodes to transmit light energy. This energy is captured by PV cells or solar panels that convert it into electrical energy, which is then stored in the battery of the EV or used directly for charging.

The effective range is a few meters, so the transmitter has to be aligned precisely with the receiver. Ambient light interferes with the system; moreover, PV cells are very expensive. The technology uses non-ionizing radiation, so health risks are minimized.

It promises greater efficiency than the conventional WPT techniques and is quite difficult to intercept or hack. Thus, it enables charging in a variety of environments, indoor as well as outdoor, and can even support charging while the vehicles are in motion. Current work includes highlight sources of high power, beam steering for dynamic charging, and light-wave WPT standards. As technology develops, we will see increased deployment of this efficient, safe, and secure charging solution in various applications. Figure.8. shows Light Wave WPT system block diagram.

The charging of EVs is attributed to the roles played by these devices in enhancing the efficiency of power transfer, contributing to the stability of the system, and also optimizing the power delivery along various distances and conditions. A wide range of compensation

Figure 8 Generic diagram of Light Wave WPT

Analysis of WPT for EV

Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) technology is steadily gaining traction in the automotive industry as a modern, safer, and less restrictive alternative to conventional plug-in chargers. Its increasing feasibility makes it a promising candidate for the future of electric vehicle (EV) charging. This review focuses on Inductive Power Transfer (IPT)—a method that transfers energy from a stationary source to an EV via magnetic fields.

The paper traces the evolution of IPT and provides insights drawn from extensive literature, detailing key design considerations, control strategies, and potential health implications associated with EV charging. The discussion emphasizes technical aspects such as coil structures and signal types, along with compensation techniques to achieve optimal efficiency. Analysis shows that circular coil configurations yield the highest power transfer performance, and a frequency of 85 kHz is suitable for high-power systems (up to 22 kW). Among various compensation techniques, the Series-Series (SS) method is widely adopted for such high-power applications.

Health and safety concerns are also addressed, alongside an overview of current standards. The paper highlights ongoing and future research directions, including enhancing transfer efficiency, reducing charging time, studying the health impact of electric fields, and improving WPT grid integration. Additionally, it discusses the potential of electrified roads for dynamic inductive charging as a long-term vision.

One study introduces a four-quadrant compact capacitive coupler for capacitive power transfer (CPT)-based EV charging. This design features vertical plates that save space and optimize power transfer through close proximity. Using LCL compensation, the system achieves high voltage and efficiency. Simulation results based on finite-element analysis demonstrated an 85.87% efficiency, with 1.88 kW output power and an air gap of up to 150 mm. Notably, the LCL configuration showed better misalignment tolerance than the previously studied LCLC system, although the latter offered slightly higher peak efficiency.

Further comparative analysis between these systems highlighted power transfer density performance and emphasized the need for future research on increasing power density and mitigating electric field radiation during the EV charging process.

Another contribution involves an impedance matching circuit (IMC), wirelessly and automatically controlled between transmitter and receiver units. This system operates at 13.56 MHz using magnetic resonance coupling and employs open-circuited 2D spiral antennas. It has applications ranging from EVs to consumer electronics. The implementation of the IMC resulted in a significant increase in power factor (PF), from 70% to 92%, while also compensating for air gap variations—though efficiency remained dependent on the alignment of resonators.

Lastly, the paper reviews a novel self-resonant coil design for high-frequency, high-power WPT tailored for EV charging. The design incorporates a fully shielded receiver coil with a thickness of just 7.1 mm, achieving an end-to-end DC-DC efficiency of 92.3%. This system reached a power density of 7.1 kW per cubic decimeter, operating at 180 kHz, thereby setting a benchmark in WPT system development.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research presents a pioneering integration capacity of WPT as a substitute for the traditional vehicle electric charging. The use of IPT systems through the implementation or integration of the circular coil designs and Series-Series topologies emphasizes their effectiveness in this regard. With a standard operation frequency set at 85 kHz, these systems are able to output 22 kW of energy and meets the recommended requirements for modern electric vehicles. The work also adds value through the development of some of the important parameters such as safety and electromagnetic interference shielding which promote WPT technology development. As a new line of research, it is less on the integration of new coils geometries but on the integration of new mechanisms for better CPT for bigger air gaps and for adaptive control.

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